

Green synthesis of silica nanoparticles and its corrosion resistance behavior on mild steel

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Abstract : In the past few years, several studies have been made in the preparation of silica from natural resources (rice husk) and its effects on purification and characterization studies. The waste materials generally have been disposed off without any environmental pollution but indeed the waste materials itself are recognized as a source of silica. In the present investigation, rice husk is subjected to sintering at 900 °C for 7 h. The sintered sample was then treated with 1 M NaOH to form sodium silicate. Finally, the gel was taken and reacted with 6 M H₂SO₄ to precipitate silica. The precipitated samples were characterized by XRD and the morphology was studied by AFM analysis. The silica coatings represent a promising approach for the development of a corrosion protective surface because of its chemical inertness, barrier properties. Silica coatings were developed on mild steel substrates by dip coating and its electrochemical behavior has been evaluated by the Tafel extrapolation method and EIS analysis using 3.5% sodium chloride solution as electrolytes. From the results, it was found that the silica coatings produced by dip coatings has excellent corrosion resistance behavior than the uncoated.

Keywords : Silica, rice husk ash, corrosion, polarization study.

Introduction

Several plant and animal extracts were isolated and tested for their potential to control corrosion and fouling. Also, different organic and inorganic inhibitor were screened for their efficiency to minimise corrosion, similarly metallic and synthesised materials as coatings, anodic deposition and impressed current method have been employed to control corrosion of metals. In the recent years, the preparation of silica from sol-gel method plays a vital role in the corrosion resistance of mild steel alloys by forming a protective layer on the surface.

Extraction of silica from rice husk is an emerging trend in the current research field. A huge amount of rice husk ash (RHA) was treated as waste and disposed off at landfill site which may leads to pollution. The carbonaceous particles produced from dust have been induced respiratory illness in human beings¹. The burning of rice husk results in the formation of rice husk ash (RHA) with SiO₂ content that varies from 85 to 98%, 10 to 40% carbon and traces of organic components depending on the burn-

ing conditions, the furnace type, the rice variety, the climate and the geographical area².

The porous nature of silica with large specific surface areas can induce various applications such as adsorption, thin layer separation, insulation and catalyst³. The main raw materials used for preparation of silica like tetraethyl orthosilicate and high purity sodium silicate are more expensive compared to cheap rice husk (RH) and RHA^{4,5}.

Hence, in the present investigation silica was prepared from RHA by treating with sodium hydroxide and sulphuric acid solution. The prepared silica was coated on mild steel by dipping method and evaluated for its corrosion resistance to introduce as biomedical applications. The corrosion protection takes place due to the synergistic effect of the silica layer along with metal surface. With the aim to explore new preparative strategies in the above topics described, the main objective of the present paper is to prepare silica nano coatings on mild steel substrate.

Experimental

Preparation of SiO_2 :

Rice husk (from rice mill) was collected from Katpadi, Vellore district, Tamilnadu, India, has been subjected to moisture removal using hot plates and sintering at $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 h. The dissolution of silica was carried out using an alkali treatment process by 1 M NaOH to obtain as sodium silicate. The resultant gel was filtered and dried in an oven for 24 h at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The precipitation of silica from sodium silicate was carried out using 6 M H_2SO_4 at pH 7 and allowed to aging for 24 h. The precipitate was centrifuged and washed with hot water and dried at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. By using X-ray diffraction method the phase formation determined.

Preparation of substrate and dipping :

The substrate mild steel was polished with 220, 600, 1000 grit SiC papers and finally by diamond paste to get the mirror like appearance and then washed and cleaned to remove adhered particles by using ultrasonication with acetone for 20 min. Finally, it was rinsed with distilled water and dried in warm air. Suspension for coating was prepared by using prepared silica with isopropyl alcohol with stirring. The substrate to be coated dipped in the suspension with required time interval and allowed to dry.

Characterization of powders :

The XRD patterns were analysed in an X-ray diffractogram (D8 model, BRUKER, Germany) using a step size of 0.02° at a scan rate of $1^\circ/\text{min}$ with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056\text{ \AA}$).

The microstructure of the prepared powders topography was determined using atomic force microscopy (Easy scan 2, Nanosurf, Switzerland).

Impedance analysis :

The experimental procedure consists of a three electrode electrochemical glass cell with the cell volume of 500 ml. The study was carried out by using 3.5% NaCl as electrolyte solution at room temperature by mild steel, platinum and SCE as working, auxiliary and reference electrodes respectively. Nyquist plot was carried out using (Gill AC Potentiostat/galvanostat frequency response analyzer, UK). The EIS measurements were performed at OCP using a frequency range from 10,000 Hz to 0.1

Hz. Nyquist plot was analyzed by software analyzer to calculate the parameters like charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) and double layer capacitance (C_{dl}).

Results and discussion

XRD analysis :

Fig. 1 shows the combined XRD results of the prepared silica from RHA. The major peaks around 22° , 27° and 40° showed the presence of quartz and cristobalite in RHA. The NaOH treated RHA was found to be in the form of hydrated and unhydrated sodium silicate glass.

Fig. 1. XRD spectra of (a) sintered RHA, (b) NaOH treated RHA and (c) H_2SO_4 treated sodium silicate.

Finally, the sodium silicate glass was treated with 6 M sulphuric acid and sintered at $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. The formation of pure silica was confirmed in the XRD spectrum with an amorphous hump between $20\text{--}30^\circ$. Fig. 2 shows the surface topography of silica prepared from RHA and have shown excellent spherical shaped particle size distribution of uniform arrangement throughout the preparation.

Electrochemical study :

Fig. 3 shows the Tafel polarization curves of mild steel and silica coated samples. The silica coating exhibits the low current density of 0.52 mA/cm^2 , compared with blank (0.89 mA/cm^2). From the graph, it was found that the corrosion inhibition of silica coating increases by many fold compared to blank. Hence, with increase in

Fig. 2. AFM image of silica for sulphuric acid treated RHA.

Fig. 3. Potentiodynamic polarization curve of blank and silica coated mild steel.

E_{corr} along with the reduction in the I_{corr} value of the silica coatings suggests its better corrosion performance on mild steel substrate.

The protection efficiency is obtained from the following equation,

$$P = \frac{I_{corr}^0 - I_{corr}}{I_{corr}^0} \times 100$$

where, I_{corr}^0 and I_{corr} are the uninhibited and inhibited

corrosion current densities respectively.

The Nyquist plot for the coated and uncoated is shown in Fig. 4. The corrosion inhibition was confirmed by the higher R_{ct} value of 5.882×10^5 Ohms for the silica coating and 3.717×10^4 Ohms for the uncoated mild steel. In connection with this, the double layer capacitance value (C_{dl}) was found to be drastically reduced from 2.345×10^{-4} Farads for the uncoated to 7.145×10^{-6} Farads for the silica coated substrate. Hence with a decrease in the C_{dl} value and with the increase in the R_{ct} value indicates its corrosion resistive behavior in an aggressive NaCl medium.

Fig. 4. Nyquist analysis of blank and silica coated mild steel.

In the presence of silica coatings, the C_{dl} values were found to decrease and this effect will result in a decrease in local dielectric constant and/or an increase in the thickness of the electrical double layer suggest that the silica coating can adhere to the surface of the metal interface. The %IE (P) was calculated from the following equation,

$$P = \frac{(1/R_{ct}^0) - (1/R_{ct})}{(1/R_{ct}^0)} \times 100$$

where R_{ct}^0 and R_{ct} are uninhibited and inhibited charge transfer resistance respectively.

Both cyclic polarization and Nyquist results were co-existed and coating shows a maximum IE of 42.72% in

Table 1. Potentiodynamic, EIS data of blank, SiO₂ on mild steel

	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} (mA/cm ²)	IE (%)	R_{ct} (Ohms)	C_{dl} (Farads)
Mild steel	-723	0.89	-	3.717×10^5	2.345×10^{-4}
SiO ₂	-389	0.52	42.72	5.882×10^5	7.145×10^{-6}

3.5% NaCl medium (Table 1). According to Murakawa and Hackerman⁶ the mild steel specimen in Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} ions environment has different adsorption behavior. They proved that the adsorption occurs through Cl^- ions have easy absorbability and inhibit corrosion than SO_4^{2-} . The nature of anions present in the solution plays a significant role in influencing the extent of adsorption. This in turn, the more adsorption of Cl^- ions on the silica coated surface results in the process of inhibition.

Conclusion

- (i) Pure silica powder with amorphous nature was prepared by dissolution and precipitation reaction with NaOH and H_2SO_4 treatment.
- (ii) The silica prepared by this method was taken for corrosion inhibition evaluation by coating on mild steel by simple dipping method. The coating has shown corrosion inhibition behavior than uncoated mild steel.

- (iii) Further, research is in progress with the increase in the concentration of silica on the mild steel substrate to increase the IE.

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